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Graduated in Biological Sciences - Teaching from the State University of Western Paran and holds a master's degree in Conservation and Management of Natural Resources from the same institution. My academic and professional trajectory encompasses areas of microbiological, physicochemical, and biochemical analyses of water, soil, food, and medicines. I have experience in Ecology, specializing in crickets and bees, with a focus on topics such as Immunology, Ecotoxicology, and Animal Behavior. Currently, I work as a laboratory technician, and my research is centered on investigating the effects of pesticides on cellular oxidative stress and the antioxidant systems present in insects

ACUTE EXPOSURE TO SUBLETHAL CONCENTRATIONS OF FENPYROXIMATE IN FOOD: IMPACT ON THE ANTIOXIDANT AND CHOLINERGIC SYSTEMS OF THE IRAÍ BEE

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Abstract

The impact of pesticides on bees and the environment is a critical concern in agricultural and ecological research. The study investigated how fenpyroximate exposure influences bees, highlighting potential risks to their health. Experiments at the Federal University of Recôncavo da Bahia (UFRB) involved *Nannotrigona testaceicornis* specimens divided into six groups of ten bees each. The study included a control group not exposed to fenpyroximate and fed only with distilled water and sugar to simulate ideal environmental conditions. Additionally, five groups were exposed to food contaminated with 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, and 3.2 ng.mL⁻¹ of Fenpyroximate, conducted in triplicate. At the end of the experimental period, the bees were euthanised by freezing. They were individually weighed and analysed for antioxidant system activity (CAT and GST), oxidative stress (LPO), and cholinergic system (AChE) following acute exposure to the active ingredient Fenpyroximate. The data were evaluated using the Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by Dunn's test ($\alpha = 0.05$). Exposure to these sublethal doses did not result in bee mortality but did induce antioxidant system activity, with significant increases in CAT activity from exposure to 0.8 ng.mL⁻¹ ($p=0.007$) and GST activity from exposure to 0.4 ng.mL⁻¹ ($p=0.024$). Consequently, the LPO reaction was reduced from 0.8 ng.mL⁻¹ ($p=0.070$). Intense induction of AChE activity was observed from 1.6 ng.mL⁻¹, potentially leading to behavioural changes such as loss of orientation and food-seeking abilities. These findings suggest that exposure to sublethal doses, significantly lower than those used in field applications, is sufficient to harm bee's health. This highlights the need to reevaluate fenpyroximate concentrations used in natural environments to mitigate adverse impacts on bee populations and ensure ecosystem sustainability.

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